

**DIALECT COMPLEX WORDS WITH
THE SUBJECTIVE RELATION OF THE
COMPONENTS IN THE UZBEK
DIALECTS OF KARAKALPAKSTAN**

Linguistics

Keywords: dialect, Uzbek dialects, semantically variety, lexical unit, dialect compound words, types of dialect compound words, homonymy.

Ibragimova Umida Yuldashevna

Teacher of Nukus State Pedagogical Institute. City Nukus, Uzbekistan.

Abstract

The given article is devoted to the scantily explored problems of dialectology of Uzbek language – the analysis of forming complex dialecticism with subordinating relationship of components in Uzbek dialects of Karakalpakstan. On the basis of analysis the number of linguistic materials is distinguished, the productive ties and fictive ways of forming complex dialectal words: noun + noun; noun=adjective; numeral + noun and etc.

In dialect word formation, along with affixed formation, complex words occupy a large place (5: 2007.5-6). In the Uzbek dialects of Karakalpakstan (hereinafter, Uzb.DK), dialect compound words are widely represented, the components of which are in a subordinate relationship. However, the nature of the design of the components of such additions does not represent uniformity. Thus, the relationship of the components of the complex word *дэвсандық* (Khodz., Kipch., Nazkh.): *уллардэжа* (Sarb., Shorh., Elk.): *нэхэн арча* (Kung., Noise., Kanlk.) “Big chest” is attribute, i.e. the first component acts as a definition of the second component, while the relationship between the components of the compound word *йэчк(и)эмэр* is a type of lizard (Khodj, Mang., Kipch., Bibz., Bern.); *иэшэкэми* (Mang., Bern., Bibz., Kilchb.): *эшэкэми* (Turtk., Elk., Sarb.) - ‘allergic disease’ is complex, objective, i.e. the first component acts as the object of the second. Such complex words in Turkology are usually called addition with attributive and complementary component relationships. The latter also includes compound words with a circumstance connection (1: 1982,20,21,82). Each of these types of addition with a subordinate ratio of components in Uzb.DK has several types and models. However, all of them, in the lexical-grammatical and semantic terms, represent a single whole with the dialect semantics.

For complex dialect words, the following features are characteristic:

1. Most of the complex dialect words proper do not contain dialect formations, each component of which is used in the literary language, without forming complex words in it: *көрпәйорындэжа* ‘third alfalfa shoot’ (Turtk., Sarb., Elk.) (Hodge., Kung., Kankk, Shamn), *ийткөйлэк* ‘first shirt, newborn child’ (Kung., Kanlk., Noise., Hodge);

2. The same words of a literary language form many dialect complex words proper: with the word *ақ* ‘white’, formed: *акбаскын* ‘ground drift’ (Kung., Kanlk., Noisy.), *ақбикэч* ‘millet’ (Kung.), *ақбилэк* ‘beauty’, *дилавар* ‘orator’, ‘improviser’ (Khodj., Kipch., Kung.), *акбуклэм* ‘white chintz’ (Hodge., Nuk. Nazkh., Kipch.), *қарасан* ‘cattle disease’ (Kung., Takrk., Nazkh.), *ақмарқа* ‘bream’ (Kung., Kanlk., Noisy., Khodj., Kipch., Nazh., Takrk., Bibz., Bern.);

3. In the formation of dialect proper complex words are involved words of the literary language, and dialect words:

a) the first component is a literary word, the second is a dialect: *темиржаба* 'vila' (Khodzh., Kung., Kipch.), compare. *a toad* is a device for pulling out hay from a stack of *мәрәзчәп* 'weed' (Khodj., Kung.), *қолжап* "small aryk' (Khodj.), *хамыртурыш* 'yeast' (Kung., Noise., Kank., Kipch., Mang.);

b) the first component is a dialect word, the second is a literary word: *гәдҗәқарын* (Khodj, Kung.), *пөлкәнән* 'a loaf of bread baked in a bakery' (Khodj, Nuk.): *кәмпәйәнән* (Kung., Noisy., Kanlk.), *сәңсәң постын* 'sheepskin coat (fur coat) is made of sheep skin' (Khodj., Kipch., Mang.);

4. As part of a number of dialect complex words, borrowed words are used:

a) the first component is the borrowed word: *ширчай* 'tea with milk' (Mang., Bibz., Bern., Naym.) from Persian "shir" 'milk', *лампамай* 'kerosene' (Khodj., Kung., Kanlk., Kipch., Bibz., Bern., Nazh.) from Persian Neft (2: 1965,113) *тиштабан* 'working boot with a low heel' (Khodj, Kung., Kanlk., Shumn.), *йәхсүв* 'winter watering of the field's water' from the Persian *yah* 'cold' (Khodj., Bibz., Bern., Sarb.);

b) the second component is the borrowed word: *ашкәди* 'pumpkin' (Turk., Elk., Sarb.), from Persian *kәdu*;

c) compound words consisting only of borrowed words: *пайтаба* 'footcloths' (Bern., Bibz., Kipch.) - from Persian *pay* leg, *tofdan* - wrap, (2: 1965,113), *әбәшәрә* 'view, appearance' (Khodj., Bibz., Bern.) from Persian *афм+фишан* 'face + appearance, look', *гәвгүм* during twilight, from tajik *зовгүм* (*gov* – cow, *gum* – missing - (4: 1981: 113.) - the time when it is difficult to find the missing cow in the dark, disappeared, *пайанул\айақ көнүр* bridge for a pedestrian (Mang. (2: 1965.113.), (Khodj., Bibz., Bern., Sarb.) from Tajik 'на, пай', share 'foot', *пул* 'bridge', *аташкүр* 'nippers for removing coal' (Khodj., Kipch., Bern.,) from Persian *аташ* 'fire', *зүр, зүр* 'take, take, hold' (3: 1971: 113 -118)

5. As part of a number of dialect complex words, there are words that have historically undergone various structural changes (truncation, affixing, building up of the base, survival forms, alternating sounds, etc.):

a) as a result of changes in the structure of the dialectal components, variants of the dialect complex words appeared: *пайстүн* 'wooden stand' (Turk., Elk., Bern.), *тәкйәмәт* 'felt', *koshma*' (Khodj., Kipch., Bern., Bibz.) from Persian *tag* – down, *namat* – "koshma";

b) as a result of a change in the structure of one of the components of a compound word of the literary language, its dialectal variants arose: lit. *тычканкуйрык* - dial. 'тычканкуйрық' local species of carrots (Khodj., Kung., Kanlk., Shumn., Nuk., Kypch.). *табанән* 'bread baked in a pan'.

As you know, among Turkologists there is quite a bit of discrepancy according to the principles of research and the classification of complex words. We adhere to the classification of complex words proposed by F. Ganiev (1: 1982, 31).

Dialect complex words in Uzb.DK differ in various types of dialect compound nouns, some of them are unproductive:

Type "noun + noun": *дарагач* 'shaft for drying things' (Khodj., Bibz., Bern.) *хыначөн* 'name of the children's game' (Kung., Kanlk., Khodj., Nazkh.), *кәрийсорақ* 'remaining grain on the current' (Khodj., Kung., Kankk.);

Type "noun + derived noun": *баишсалма* 'head *aryk* from Chigir' (Bibz., Bern.), *нантуврама* 'type of food', *темирсувлық* 'bit' (Khodj., Kipch., Bern.),

Type "noun + adjective" *ичқара*, *йүзиқара*, *кәвниқара*, *йолыбузық*, *кәвнийарым* 'offended', 'without mood' (Mang., Kilchb., Bibz., Bern. Kilchn.);

Type "root adjective + noun": *қаққурт* 'white cheese' (Khodj., Kung., Kanlk.), *қазәрик* 'dried apricots, essential apricot', *қарамчөн* 'common name for weed' (Khodj., Kung., Kankk.), *йавайот* (Turk., Elk., Bern., Bibz.), *қызылмағыз* 'melon variety' (Bern., Man., Kalk.), *қарапочақ* 'melon's disease', *ләккитавақ* 'small glazed cup' (Bibz., Bern., Elk.), Sarb., Shorh.);

Type "adjective + adjective": *қаракир* is very dirty (Kipch., Bibz., Bern., Nazkh., Khodj.), *қарачунак* 'wheat variety', *қарақотыр* 'cattle disease' (Khodj., Kung., Mang.) *сараврув* 'jaundice' (Khodj., Kung., Kanlk., Shumn.): *сармас* (Mang., Kilchb., Bibz., Bern. Sarb.), *қарақатты* 'kind of melon' (Khodj., Kipch., Kung.);

Type "derivative adjective + noun": *зыйаллыджәндик* 'predators' (Khodj., Noise. Kalk., Kung.), *қаллықөл* 'carrying lake' (Kanlk., Kung., Khodj.);

Type "numeral + noun": *үччәйрәк* 'one's area' (Kipch., Mang., Nazkh., Khodj.), *үчәм қозы* (khodj., Kipch., Nazh., Mang., Bibz.), *бәшбармақ* 'type of food' (Khodj., Kung., Kalk., Nuk.),

Type "numeral + participial form": *бирқырқар* 'late-lamb lamb' (Chap.), *биртувған* 'pedigree camel': *тишйарған*, *тишбузған*:ди:ш бузан 'dish';

Type "verb + noun": *буктизә* 'device for training horses' (Kung.), *уртоқмақ* 'truncheon' (Naym.), *есерсоқ* 'crazy', 'bad' (Khodj., Nuk., Kanlk., Kung.);

The following types are found, many of which are unproductive:

Type "adverb + adverb": *дүстәмән* 'down' (Kung., Kanlk., Khodj.), *нәгәнда* 'occasionally' (Kung., Kanlk., Nuk.), *йәңгәл* 'first' (Mang., Bibz., Bern.), *атамзаман* 'long ago' (Kung., Kanlk., Nuk., Khodj.): *әлмисақ* (Mang., Bibz., Bern., Sarb.);

Type "numeral + adverb": *бирзаматта* / *бир майданда* "at one moment" (Bern., Sarb.), *йэкибаиштан* "indisputably", "unconditionally" (Kipch., Khodj. Bibz., Bern.) , "unconditionally" (Khodj., Kipch., Nazkh.).

Type "noun + noun": *жылдың жылы* 'annually', *айагүсти* 'in a hurry' (Khodj, Mang., Bibz., Bern.);

There are a number of more unproductive types of complex dialectal adverbs: *муздай аман* 'safely' (Uzun.), *муз каракәсәк* 'very cold' (Khodj., Kipch., Bibz., Mang.), *хәддән тыш* 'beyond strength' (Hodge., Nuk., Bibz., Bern., Mang.)

Dialectic complex words related to the rest of speech are also unproductive. So, with the participation of the pronouns formed: *йэчкайда* 'nowhere' (Khodj., Kipch.), *йэчким* 'no one', *йэссат* 'nothing', (Khodj., Kipch., Nazkh.), *незат* 'what is', *йэчким* 'no one', *кимтуртти* 'name of the game children' (Khodj., Kipch., Bibz.), with the modal word *дәжоқ* – *урыжәок* the humor 'no desire', *кәмийоқ* 'decent'

The first components of dialectal complex words with the attribute relations of components are the words of almost all parts of speech, which differ only in their productivity. In the lexical terms, the first components of compound words belong to different categories. This can be illustrated by the example of dialect compound nouns, the first components of which denote the following:

1. The form of the object, expressed by the second component: *атжал* 'flaw'. (Khodj., Nazh., Bibz.). "horse + mane", i.e. a narrow strip of grass, missed when mowing, resembles a horse's mane; *аюджылан* 'large poisonous snake' (Kanlk., Kung., Noise., Khodj.), lit. bear + snake; *атавыз* 'pliers, tongs, vise' (Khodj., Kipch., Mang., Bern.) it is *horse mouth*;

2. The material of the object expressed by the second component: *мистаба* 'tray for a samovar' (Bern., Bibz., Nazh., Khodj.) "honey + pan", i.e. frying pan (tray) made from honey. Compare *таштабак* 'cup made of clay' (Khodj., Kung., Kipch., Mang., Bern.) made of clay, *чальқора* 'shed', 'pen', built of reed or rod (Khodj. Kipch. Nazh., Kung., Kalk.);

3. Purpose of the subject: *дәжайнамаз* 'nightmare for prayer' (Turt., Bern., Nazkh., Khodj.), *аяққап* 'footwear' (Kung., Kanlk., Noisy., Khodj.), *ийнағач* 'yoke' (Khodj., Kipch., Kung.), *аштақта* 'board for making doughs';

4. Quality, property of the item indicated by the second component: *қақчәккә* 'thin, weak' (Khodj., Kipch., Bibz., Bern.), *харамчәп* 'common name for weed' (Khodj., Kipch., Nazh.);

5. The position, the state of the object, expressed by the second component: *қышамқозы* 'Lamb of the late' (Bern., Bibz., Mang., Khodj.), *жугирмә качар* 'heifer' (Takrk.), *ақабасув* 'abundant water' (Khodj. Kipch. , Kung., Mang.), *қарамай* 'pitch' (Khodj., Nazkh., Kipch., Kung.);

6. Place of origin, origin of the item indicated by the second component: *ширзурич* 'rice porridge with milk' (Turk., Sarb.), *найман жүвәри* 'view of zhugary' (Hodge., Mang., Kilchb.), *бухары баиш* 'type of winter wheat. ';

7. The time of action of the subject, indicated by the second component: *күн түн* 'all day', *таңһэртәң* 'tomorrow' (Turk.), *таңмә:л* 'early in the morning' (Kung., Nazkh., Nuk.), *талтүш* 'exactly lunch time' (Khodj., Kipch): *чанқайтүш* (Kung., Kanlk., Nuk., Takrk.);

8. The species ratio of the object, expressed by the second component: *бүргәбалық* 'small fish' (Khodj.), *доңызот* 'dark brown weed color' (Khodj., Kipch., Kung., Kanklk.), *дәжәлкесу* 'water in the head арык' (Kung., Kanlk., Khodj.);

9. The result of the action of the subject indicated by the second component: *ташкәкил* 'firm surety', *аләнкә* 'lung disease', *пахтамай* 'vegetable oil' (Bern., Khodj., Bibz.): *ақмай* (Nuk., Shumn., Kanlk., Kung.), *доңмай / тоңмай* 'fat', *сүтәмгән* 'six month old baby '(Khodj., Kung., Kanlk.);

10. The subject of possession expressed by the second component: *кәгәриш сувы* 'first irrigation for cotton field' (Mang., Bern.), *торғай оты* 'grass growing on salt marsh' (Khodo., Nazkh.), *чи:ит майы* 'cottonseed oil' (Turk., Bern., Elk.);

11. The volume, the quantity of the item indicated by the second component: the *бир кулак сув* 'small water for irrigation' (Tarb.), *килакаса* 'liter drinking bowl' (Kipch., Khodzh., Nazkh.), *бир қыйтақ дәжер* 'one piece of land' (Djuv.);

12. The color of the object, expressed by the second component: *алабарыс* 'clay terrain', *акбайпак* 'general disease of cattle' (Kilchb.), *аққув* 'swan', *бозторғай* 'bird', *ақбаиш* 'grass growing on the saline', *карақаш* 'ethnonym' (Hodge., Nuk.), *кара тырышмай* 'cholera', (gkt), *кәгәгиш* 'vegetable growing';

Such complex words are mainly complex verbs and nouns, between the components of which are observed objective and adverbial relations.

In the formation of complex (compound) verbs from different parts of speech, nouns and adjectives are most often the first components, and the auxiliary verbs are the second components. In conjunction with the nominal words, the auxiliary verbs are *бол-* "be", "stand up", *сал-* "put", "lay", *қыл-* "do", *әт-* "do", less productive, *ал-* "take", *чық-* "out", unproductive *қой-* 'put ', *йаса-* ' do', 'create ', *кел-* 'come', *бар-* 'to go', *ач-* 'to open', *йур-* 'to go', 'to walk', *қал-*to stay, *түш-* 'to go down' and others. F.A.Ganiev calls them "functionally auxiliary verbs, meaning that they are full-valued verbs, only in the process of formation of complex verbs appearing as auxiliary verbs" (1: 1982.88).

The noun type + verb *бол-* has the meaning 'do', which is expressed by the first component: *пучбол-* 'wither', 'wither' (about cereals), *әгәбол-* 'rationally', *бақна бол-* 'obey'.

The type "noun + verb *сал-* with meaning to produce an action expressed by the first component: *ам сал-* 'to conduct secret negotiations', *бас сал-* 'to speak immediately', 'to beat about the mortgage'.

Type "noun + verb *қыл-* with the meaning "to accomplish what is expressed by the first component": *зыйан қыл-* 'cause harm', *абай қыл-* 'take care', *төнкәриш қыл-* / *авдарыш қыл-* 'turn over'.

The type "noun + verb *эм-* with the meaning "to produce an action or process expressed by the first component": *давуи эм-* 'mourn', *ҳәз иэм-* 'to happy', *мыңқ иэмийди* 'silent', *әпүэт* 'excuse'.

In summary, the types of dialect complex words with a subordinate ratio of components, are widely represented in Uzb.DK, differ in terms of lexical and semantic structure and interrelationship of components. In the material studied, the productive types of complex nouns with an attribute and complex verbs with a complementary relation of components are mainly presented. Complex adjectives and adverbs are less productive. Homonymic and synonymous relations are also established between complex words that have dialect and also dialectically nationwide.

References

1. Ganiyev F.A. *Obrazovaniye slojnyh slov v tatarskom yazyke*. – M.: Nauka, 1982.
2. Ishayev A. *Iz leksiki uzbekskih govorov Karakalpakii \ \ Sb: Voprosy tyurkologii*. – Tashkent: Izd-vo: Nauka, 1966.
3. O'zbek tilining dialektologik lug'ati. – Toshkent: Fan, 1971.
4. O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati. – Toshkent: O'zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi, 2008.
5. Hojiyev A. *O'zbek tili so'z yasash tizimi*. – Toshkent: O'qituvchi.2007.

Abbreviations

Bern. – Beruniy region of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

Bibz. – village Bibiazar in Beruniy region.

Kanlk. – Kanlikol region of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

Kung. - Kungrad region of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

Sarb. – Sarabiy village in Ellikkala region of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

Turt. – Turtkul region of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

Mang. – Amudarya region of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

Khodj. – Khodjeyli region of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

Elk. – Ellikkala region of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.